

MODERN MODELS OF ORGANIZING PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

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Abstract. *This article focuses on how public procurement should be organized with modern methods.*

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The public procurement system of each country is implemented on the basis of a certain model. Summarizing the shopping models of the countries of the world today, we can see that they are mainly of 3 types:

1. Centralized model;
2. Decentralized model;
3. Mixed model.

Orders for goods (work, services) that must be purchased in a centralized procurement model are made by a specially authorized organization or a specific structural unit of the government (local authority, ministry, committee, agency, etc.). For example, the Ministry of Public Education centrally orders textbooks to publishers for more than 10,000 schools in the country. Or, the Ministry of Health centrally orders medicines and medical diagnostic equipment for lower medical institutions, and then distributes and supplies them based on the needs of lower units. An example of this is that corporate structures with a state share of more than 50% in their charter purchase some goods (work, service) centrally and then deliver them to lower branches.

In the centralized model, the higher authority (organization) gathers the needs for a specific product (work, service) from the lower organizations and orders an integrated purchase. In some large state customers, a special department dealing only with purchases (purchase department in most joint-stock companies and companies) is formed.

There are a number of advantages to making purchases in a centralized model. For example:

-in the centralized model, since a large-scale wholesale order is placed, the purchased goods (work, service) are obtained at a low price;

-highly qualified specialists of the special commission established by the ministry or higher authorities study the quality, suitability or reliability of the supplier of the purchased goods (work, service) and then place an order;

-due to the large volume of orders, transportation, installation, insurance costs for one unit of goods (work, service) are small, etc.

There are advantages and disadvantages to purchasing in a centralized model. For example:

-in the centralized model, due to the large volume of orders, the delivered goods (products) may contain invalid and low-quality ones. When receiving the order, it is not possible to physically check each product (in school textbooks, some pages are not cut, books are glued upside down, there is a smaller amount of drugs in the medicine container than the norm, clothes are smaller than the measurement (size) or there are cases such as large stitches);

-the goods (products) purchased centrally by higher authorities may not all correspond to the needs of lower units (for example, when budget organizations express their needs for computer equipment or tables and chairs to the higher authority and expect the most modern, convenient goods, cases such as providing them with products that are cheaper or cause some inconvenience in use).

-when purchases are made centrally, the needs of the subordinate departments are usually summarized, and then the order is placed. In addition, due to the size of the order, the necessary goods (work, services) may be delivered late, etc.

When purchasing purchases based on a **centralized model**, each state customer independently implements the necessary goods (work, services) based on established requirements and procedures. For example, each district finance department, each higher education institution, each bank branch will be able to purchase the goods (work, services) they need on the basis of the established legal requirements.

There are also advantages to making purchases in a **decentralized model**. For example:

- in the decentralized model, the need for goods (work, services) is satisfied a little faster;
- responsibility for purchased goods (work, services) lies directly with this customer;
- based on existing conditions and opportunities, it will be possible to purchase goods (work, services) suitable for one's needs, etc.

Purchasing in a decentralized model also has its *drawbacks*. For example:

- in the decentralized model, the price of purchased goods (work, services) can sometimes be expensive due to small orders;
- each state customer is allowed to make independent purchases, sometimes low-quality goods (work, services) with a short warranty period may be purchased due to the customer's inexperience;

-when purchases are carried out in a decentralized manner, sometimes representatives of customers may conclude unfair contracts for their personal interests, there may be cases of illegal embezzlement of funds, etc.

In the **mixed model**, purchases are made in cooperation with a state customer and a specialized organization. For example, when budget organizations in Uzbekistan place an order for goods (work, services), the Treasury of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan confirms that funds are provided for these goods (work, services), and that there are sufficient funds in the customer's account. then an announcement will be made. Or, in cases where the value of goods (works, services) exceeds twenty-five thousand (six thousand for budget customers) times the amount of the basic calculation, technical assignments for state procurement for examination in accordance with the procedure established by law. Republic of Uzbekistan Economic development and poverty reduction will be sent to the state unitary enterprise "Center for Comprehensive Expertise of Projects and Import Contracts" under the Ministry. The procurement announcement will be posted only after receiving a positive conclusion of the Comprehensive Expertise Center on the technical assignment for public procurement.

There are several advantages of making purchases in a mixed model. For example:

- ineffective and illegal spending of funds is avoided in the mixed model;
- highly qualified specialists of the special commission established by the ministry or higher authorities study the quality, suitability or reliability of the supplier of the purchased goods (work, service) and then place an order;

-implementation of current control over purchased goods (work, services) is ensured, etc.

The mixed model has advantages as well as disadvantages. For example:

-in the mixed model, procurement may be delayed due to the fact that the period of obtaining permission from the responsible or specialized organization is sometimes extended;

-in this model, electronic document circulation is established between the customer, specialized organization and operators of special information portals, sometimes problems related to electricity supply, technical and internet speed in remote districts, and inconveniences in purchasing can give birth, etc.

Conclusion:

From what has been analyzed above it can be inferred that these methods have their own advantageous superiority to apply. It depends on the appropriaty of the procurement and preference.

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